

PROMPT ENGINEERING

Version 1

Extract information about the use of large language models (LLMs) in qualitative analysis based on the questions below. The goal is to understand the state of the art in using LLMs for this type of analysis. Follow the topics and provide direct and concise answers.

For each question, seek relevant excerpts in the analyzed article, synthesize the information found, and provide a clear and objective response for each question.

Questions:

1. Application Context:

- What was the context and primary objective of the study when applying LLMs in qualitative analysis?
- What was the context or domain in which the LLM was used for qualitative analysis?
- What was the main goal of the study when employing LLMs in this context?
- Did the authors provide justifications for using LLMs instead of traditional qualitative analysis methods?

2. Model Configuration and Data:

- Which LLM model was used (e.g., GPT, BERT) and what specific version?
- Was the model fine-tuned or adapted for the study?
- What were the sources of data analyzed (e.g., interviews, social media, documents)?

3. Analysis Methodology:

- How was the qualitative analysis process conducted using the LLM?
- Were specific techniques or methodologies employed to support the analysis (e.g., automatic coding, theme extraction)?
- Was any established qualitative analysis framework used (e.g., content analysis, grounded theory)?

4. Evaluation and Results:

- What metrics or criteria were used to assess the effectiveness of the LLM in qualitative analysis?
- Did the study compare LLMs with traditional qualitative analysis methods? What were the results?
- What were the key conclusions about using LLMs for qualitative analysis?

5. Limitations and Challenges:

- Were specific limitations identified in using LLMs for qualitative analysis? **Yes / Partially / No** (Justify)
- Were technical or methodological challenges mentioned in applying LLMs?

6. Future Directions:

- Are there recommendations or suggestions from the authors for the future use or development of LLMs in qualitative analyses?

Version 2

Extract information about the use of large language models (LLMs) in qualitative analysis based on the questions below. The goal is to understand the state of the art in using LLMs for this type of analysis. Follow the topics and provide direct and concise answers.

For each question, search for relevant excerpts in the analyzed article, synthesize the information found, and provide a clear and objective response. If the answer to the first question is **NO**, do not respond to the subsequent questions.

Questions:

1. Is the primary focus of the study on analyzing the use of LLMs to support qualitative data analysis? **Yes / Partially / No** (Justify)
2. What was the context and primary objective of the study when applying LLMs in qualitative analysis?
3. Which LLM model was used (e.g., GPT, BERT) and what specific version?
4. Was the model fine-tuned or adapted for the study?
5. What were the sources of data analyzed (e.g., interviews, social media, documents)?
6. How was the qualitative analysis process conducted using the LLM?
7. Were specific techniques or methodologies employed to support the analysis (e.g., automatic coding, theme extraction)?
8. Was any established qualitative analysis framework used (e.g., content analysis, grounded theory)?
9. What metrics or criteria were used to assess the effectiveness of the LLM in qualitative analysis?
10. Did the study compare LLMs with traditional qualitative analysis methods? What were the results?
11. What were the key conclusions about using LLMs for qualitative analysis?
12. Were specific limitations identified in using LLMs for qualitative analysis? **Yes / Partially / No** (Justify)
13. Are there recommendations or suggestions from the authors for the future use or development of LLMs in qualitative analysis?

Version 3

Extract information about the use of large language models (LLMs) in qualitative analysis based on the questions below. The goal is to understand the state of the art in using LLMs for this type of analysis. Follow the topics and provide direct and concise answers.

For each question, search for relevant excerpts in the analyzed article, synthesize the

information found, and provide a clear and objective response. If the answer to the first question is **NO**, do not respond to the subsequent questions.

Questions:

1. Is the primary focus of the study on analyzing the use of LLMs to support qualitative data analysis? **Yes / Partially / No** (Justify)
2. What was the context and primary objective of the study when applying LLMs in qualitative analysis?
3. Which LLM model was used and what specific version?
4. Was the model fine-tuned or adapted for the study?
5. What were the sources of data analyzed (e.g., interviews, social media, documents)?
6. How was the qualitative analysis process conducted using the LLM?
7. Were specific techniques or methodologies employed to support the analysis (e.g., automatic coding, theme extraction)?
8. Was any established qualitative analysis framework used (e.g., content analysis, grounded theory)?
9. What metrics or criteria were used to assess the effectiveness of the LLM in qualitative analysis?
10. Did the study compare LLMs with traditional qualitative analysis methods? What were the results?
11. What were the key conclusions about using LLMs for qualitative analysis?
12. Were specific limitations identified in using LLMs for qualitative analysis? **Yes / Partially / No** (Justify)
13. Are there recommendations or suggestions from the authors for the future use or development of LLMs in qualitative analysis?

Version 4

This prompt extracts information about the use of large language models (LLMs) in qualitative analysis based on the research questions (RQs) outlined below. The goal is to understand the state of the art in using LLMs for qualitative analysis. Provide clear and concise answers for each question based on the analyzed article. If the answer to the initial question is **NO**, skip the remaining questions for that section.

RQ.1: What is the context in which LLMs have been applied to support qualitative analysis?

- Is the primary focus of the study on analyzing the use of LLMs to support qualitative data analysis? **Yes / Partially / No** (Justify)
- What was the context and primary objective of the study when applying LLMs in qualitative analysis?

RQ.2: What LLM model, configuration, and data sources were used?

- Which LLM model was used and what specific version?

- Was the model fine-tuned or adapted for the study?
- What were the sources of data analyzed (e.g., interviews, social media, documents)?

RQ.3: How was the LLM used to conduct qualitative analysis, and which techniques or methodologies were applied?

- How was the qualitative analysis process conducted using the LLM?
- Were specific techniques or methodologies employed to support the analysis (e.g., automatic coding, theme extraction)?
- Was any established qualitative analysis framework used (e.g., content analysis, grounded theory)?

RQ.4: How was the effectiveness of the LLM assessed, and what were the main results?

- What metrics or criteria were used to assess the effectiveness of the LLM in qualitative analysis?
- Did the study compare LLMs with traditional qualitative analysis methods? What were the results?
- What were the key conclusions about using LLMs for qualitative analysis?

RQ.5: What limitations and future research directions were reported?

- Were specific limitations identified in using LLMs for qualitative analysis? **Yes / Partially / No** (Justify)
- Are there recommendations or suggestions from the authors for the future use or development of LLMs in qualitative analysis?

Version 5

Extract responses to the questions below regarding the use of large language models (LLMs) in qualitative analysis based on the provided article. Follow the given response options. Be direct and concise in the questions without predefined answer choices. If the answer to the first question is **NO**, do not respond to the subsequent questions.

RQ.1: In what context have LLMs been applied to support qualitative analysis?

- Is the primary focus of the study on using LLMs to support qualitative data analysis? **Yes / Partially / No** (Justify)
- What was the context of the qualitative analysis (application domain)? **Education, Health, Culture, Law, Technology, Software Engineering, Others**
- What was the main objective of the study in applying LLMs for qualitative analysis? **Options to be provided**

RQ.2: What LLM model, configuration, and data sources were used?

- Which LLM model was used? **ChatGPT, LIAMA, NVivo, Atlas, Others**

- Was the model fine-tuned or adapted for the study? **Yes / Partially / No**
- What were the data sources analyzed? **Interviews, Social Media, Documents, Others**

RQ.3: How was the LLM used to conduct qualitative analysis, and which techniques or methodologies were applied?

- How was the qualitative analysis process conducted using the LLM?
- Were specific techniques/methodologies used to support the analysis? **Yes / Partially / No**
- What techniques were used to support the analysis? **Open Coding, Axial Coding, Deductive Coding, Theme Extraction, Topic Extraction, Others**
- Was any established qualitative analysis framework used? **Content Analysis, Discourse Analysis, Grounded Theory, Others**

RQ.4: How was the effectiveness of the LLM assessed, and what were the main results?

- What metrics or criteria were used to evaluate the effectiveness of the LLM in qualitative analysis?
- Did the study compare LLMs with traditional qualitative analysis methods? **Yes / Partially / No**
- If the answer to the previous question is **Yes**, what were the results?

RQ.5: What limitations and future research directions were reported?

- Were specific limitations identified in using LLMs for qualitative analysis? **Yes / Partially / No** (Justify)
- Are there recommendations or suggestions from the authors for the future use or development of LLMs in qualitative analysis? **Yes / Partially / No** (Justify)

Version 6

Extract responses to the questions below regarding the use of large language models (LLMs) in qualitative analysis based on the provided article. Follow the given response options. Be direct and concise in your responses without predefined answer choices. If the answer to the first question is **NO** or **PARTIALLY**, skip the remaining questions.

Questions:

1. **Is the primary focus of the study on analyzing the use of LLMs to support qualitative data analysis?**
Yes / Partially / No (Justify)
2. **What was the context of the qualitative analysis?**
Education, Health, Culture, Law, Technology, Software Engineering, Others

3. **What was the main objective of the study in applying LLMs for qualitative analysis?**
Compare with manual analysis, Automate analysis, Evaluate capability, Others
4. **Which LLM model was used?**
ChatGPT, LIAMA, NVivo, Atlas, BERT, Others
5. **Was the model fine-tuned or adapted for the study?**
Yes / Partially / No
6. **What data sources were analyzed?**
Interviews, Social Media, Documents, Others
7. **How was the qualitative analysis process conducted using the LLM?**
8. **Were specific techniques/methodologies used to support the analysis?**
Yes / Partially / No
9. **What techniques were used or evaluated?**
Open Coding, Axial Coding, Deductive Coding, Theme Extraction, Topic Extraction, Categorization, Others
10. **Was any established qualitative analysis framework used?**
Content Analysis, Discourse Analysis, Grounded Theory, Others
11. **What metrics or criteria were used to assess the effectiveness of the LLM in qualitative analysis?**
Comparison with human analysis, Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1 Score, Others
12. **Did the study compare LLMs with traditional qualitative analysis methods?**
Yes / No
13. **If the answer to question 12 is yes, was the LLM better, worse, or equal to traditional methods?**
14. **Were specific limitations identified in using LLMs for qualitative analysis?**
Yes / No (Justify in bullet points)
15. **Are there recommendations or suggestions from the authors for the future use or development of LLMs in qualitative analysis?**
Yes / No (Justify in bullet points)

FINAL VERSION

Extract responses to the questions below regarding the use of large language models (LLMs) in qualitative analysis based on the provided article. Follow the given response options. Be direct and concise in your responses without predefined answer choices. If the answer to the first question is **NO** or **PARTIALLY**, skip the remaining questions.

Questions:

1. **Is the primary focus of the study on analyzing the use of LLMs to support qualitative data analysis?**
Yes / Partially / No (Justify)
2. **What was the context of the qualitative analysis?**
Education, Health, Culture, Law, Technology, Software Engineering, Others

3. **What was the main objective of the study in applying LLMs for qualitative analysis?**
Compare with manual analysis, Automate analysis, Evaluate capability, Others
4. **Which LLM model was used?**
ChatGPT, LIAMA, NVivo, Atlas, Others
5. **Was the model fine-tuned or adapted for the study?**
Yes / Partially / No
6. **What data sources were analyzed?**
Interviews, Social Media, Documents, Others
7. **How was the qualitative analysis process conducted using the LLM?**
8. **Were specific techniques/methodologies used to support the analysis?**
Yes / Partially / No
9. **What techniques were used or evaluated?**
Open Coding, Axial Coding, Deductive Coding, Theme Extraction, Topic Extraction, Categorization, Others
10. **Was any established qualitative analysis framework used?**
Content Analysis, Discourse Analysis, Grounded Theory, Others
11. **Does the article detail the prompt engineering process?**
Yes / No
12. **What metrics or criteria were used to assess the effectiveness of the LLM in qualitative analysis?**
Comparison with human analysis, Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1 Score, Others
13. **Did the study compare LLMs with traditional qualitative analysis methods?**
Yes / No
14. **If the answer to question 13 is yes, was the LLM better, worse, or equal to traditional methods?**
15. **Were specific limitations identified in using LLMs for qualitative analysis?**
Yes / No (Justify in bullet points)
16. **Are there recommendations or suggestions from the authors for the future use or development of LLMs in qualitative analysis?**
Yes / No (Justify in bullet points)